

Statistical report from the conducted research
“Housing decisions – behavioral aspects of choices and price expectations”

Dr. Joanna Waszczuk
Warsaw School of Economics

Warsaw, 28/10/2023

Contents

- 1. Introduction..... 3
- 2. Organization of research work..... 4
- 3. Description of the trial 4
- 4. The research results 6
- 5. Conclusions..... 13
- 6. Literature :..... 15

1. Introduction

So far, theoretical and empirical research on the demand side of the residential real estate market has been conducted primarily from a macroeconomic perspective (see Case and Shiller 1988 et al.), while on a microeconomic scale it concerned primarily housing preferences (see Kauko 2006, Trojanek 2009, et al.). However, there is little microeconomic empirical research on housing decisions and price expectations of buyers, with particular emphasis on their behavioral aspects.

The aim of the work was to conduct a pilot study on the declared determinants of housing decision-making processes and price expectations of households. The scientific activity focused on three aspects of the demand side of the residential real estate market.

First, factors influencing housing decisions were identified. Se focused on choices regarding the form of property ownership (rental vs. ownership) and expectations regarding the potential change of both the form of ownership and the type or characteristics of the property, due to households' needs. Secondly, price expectations were examined, which provided the basis for formulating conclusions regarding price-setting processes in the residential real estate market. Thirdly, the sources from which households obtain information about prices on the residential real estate market were identified. The anchoring effect, which involves relying on some information and adjusting to it, was also empirically examined. Therefore, the tendency of households to revise their expectations after receiving new information that may differ from their previous knowledge about the market was checked.¹

The research work was carried out with the support of the Miniatura 6 grant from the National Science Center number 2022/06/X/HS4/00667.

¹ The results will be published as a scientific article entitled: Behavioral aspects of price expectations and the anchoring effect on the housing market – Polish case study in the scientific journal *Housing, Theory, Society*.

2. Organization of research work

In order to obtain conclusions regarding issues related to housing decisions, it was decided to conduct an empirical study and collect the necessary data. As part of the scientific activity, a survey questionnaire was created by the person conducting the research, an external company was selected to collect data, and then the data was analyzed. The pilot study questionnaire consisted of 37 questions for the control sample and 39 questions for the research sample divided into three thematic sections. The surveyed population was 1,000 households living in a large Polish city (over 450,000 inhabitants - Gdańsk, Kraków, Poznań, Warsaw, Wrocław), according to the structure of the housing stock in these towns. 750 people constituted the research group that was used to verify the hypothesis regarding the price anchoring effect on the real estate market. The survey was conducted on December 19-26, 2022 using the CAWI method (on-line).

3. Description of the trial

Data was collected (gathered from 1,000 respondents), and the sample structure are presented in Table 1. The average age of the respondent is 40 years. In accordance with the guidelines provided to the external company, entities aged 18-65 were examined. Households of the surveyed units consisted of from 1 to 7 people, with an average of approximately 2.85 people, i.e. a couple with a child. According to the survey design the structure of the sample was to be balanced by sex variable. Therefore, 51% of women and 49% of men were tested. The majority of the sample, as much as 51%, were people in formal relationships (husband/wife). The second largest group were singles (24%). The fewest were widowers (4%) and people with a different marital status. For most respondents, the form of employment is an employment contract for an indefinite period (60%) or a fixed-term employment contract (14%). A relatively small part of the group consisted of people who owned the company. When it comes to gross income per person, most of the sample has incomes of PLN 3,001-5,000 (26%) and PLN 5,001-7,500 (23%). As many as 45% of the surveyed people assess their financial situation as average, and slightly less, as many as 32%, claim that their situation is good. Moreover, according to the survey results, 72% of the survey participants own an apartment, while 28% of people reported that they do not own an apartment.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the sample

Variable	Definition	In:	Descriptive statistics					
			Min	1Q	Median	Mean	3Q	Max
Age	The age of the person	years	18	31	37	40	50	65
Household size	Number of family members	Number	1	2	3	2.85	4	7
	Categories	In:				Share		
Sex	Man	%				0.49		
	Woman					0.51		
Marital status	Married	%				0.51		
	Cohabitant					0.13		
	Single					0.24		
	Widower					0.04		
	Divorced					0.07		
	Other					0.01		
Employment	Employment contract for an indefinite period	%				0.60		
	Employment contract for a fixed period					0.14		
	Self-employment					0.08		
	Company owner					0.02		
	Pensioner					0.04		
	Unemployed					0.06		
	Professionally inactive					0.06		
Gross per capita income	<2000	%				0.07		
	2001-3000					0.17		
	3001-5000					0.26		
	5001-7500					0.23		
	7501-10000					0.09		
	10001-15000					0.07		
	15001-20000					0.03		
	>=20001					0.02		
	No answer					0.04		
Assessment of the financial situation	Bad	%				0.14		
	Average					0.45		
	All right					0.32		
	Very good					0.08		
Do you have an apartment?	NO	%				0.28		
	Yes					0.72		

Source: Own study

The respondents came from different cities, and it had reflected the structure of the housing stock, in accordance with the assumptions of the research project. The largest number of respondents were from Warsaw (approx. 37%), Kraków (approx. 16%), Wrocław (13.4%), Łódź (13.3%), Poznań (approx. 11%), and the least from Gdańsk (9.6%).

Chart 1. Share of respondents in the sample from Polish cities

Source: Own study

4. The research results

One of the goals of the pilot study was to answer the question of how households would like to meet their housing needs. 55% of people were in favor of owning a flat. If we go deeper into this answer, it turns out that 24.4% of respondents were definitely in favor of ownership. 31.6% of respondents indicated ownership with some uncertainty. Only 8.9% of individuals would definitely choose renting. An interesting observation is the group of 13.6% of respondents who did not have a clear preference and indicated the "I don't know" option.

Chart 2. Housing preferences of households

Source: Own study

Respondents were also asked how they currently meet their housing needs. It turned out that in the entire sample, approximately 65% of individuals live in the apartment they own, while approximately 18% of individuals rent the entire apartment and approximately 3% rent a room. Usually, these are students or individuals in the initial phase of their career who have not decided yet if they want to live with a given city. People living with their parents still constitute a large part of the sample, as much as 10%.

Chart 3. How do you meet your housing needs

Source: Own study

There was a suspicion that the answer to the question about how to meet housing needs may show some spatial diversity, hence the results were presented by city where the respondents live. It turned out that approximately 60%-70% of individuals live in the premises they own. Between 15% and 27% of individuals rent their entire apartment, while approximately 1% - 4.5% rent a room. People living with their parents still constitute a large part of the sample, as much as 7%-13.5%.

Chart 4. How do you meet your housing needs in a given city.

Source: Own study

It turns out that a large part of the respondents in the sample do not plan to buy a flat in the coming years (approx. 44%). The rest have such plans in the near future. Within the next 2 years, 13.0% of respondents intend to purchase an apartment. These plans are postponed to a slightly later period of 2-4 years for 16.1%, and to 5-10 years for approximately 19.4%.

Table 2. When are you planning to buy a flat?

No	When are you planning to buy an apartment?	%
1	2-4 years	16.1%
2	5-10 years	19.4%
3	up to 2 years	13.0%
4	I don't plan	44.0%
5	over 10 years	7.5%

Source: Own study

When we asked what was most important when choosing an apartment 32.8% of respondents said price. Therefore, respondents note the significant impact of budget constraints when purchasing real estate. What is also quite important is the cost of living, location and standard of the apartment. However, the standard of the building and the layout of the apartment turned out to be less important for the surveyed units.

Table 3. Rankings of preferences for features when choosing an apartment

No	Preference	Ranking 1	Ranking 2	Ranking 3	Ranking 4	Ranking 5	Ranking 6	Ranking 7
1	apartment price	32.8%	16.8%	16.0%	12.6%	8.2%	7.5%	6.1%
2	maintenance costs	13.7%	18.8%	15.3%	13.8%	11.6%	13.8%	13.0%
3	location of the apartment	18.5%	16.1%	15.1%	14.0%	14.9%	11.8%	9.6%
4	square area of the apartment	10.7%	16.9%	15.6%	16.4%	15.3%	13.5%	11.6%
5	apartment layout	4.6%	7.9%	10.4%	14.1%	16.6%	20.6%	25.8%
6	technical condition of the building	5.7%	11.2%	12.2%	15.7%	18.6%	17.9%	18.7%
7	apartment standard	14.0%	12.3%	15.4%	13.4%	14.8%	14.9%	15.2%

Source: Own study

To examine whether in Poland, as in more developed countries, households perceive the housing as a form of investment, we asked about it, both directly and indirectly. Usually households feeling inflation and wanting to preserve the value of their savings try to invest cash, and the real estate market is perceived as a good investment of capital. It turns out that Poles have a completely different opinion. When asked about the impact of inflation on housing decisions, as many as 56% said that high inflation discourages purchases, while only 15% felt encouraged. This means that respondents do not think in terms of investing money, they only notice financial constraints.

Chart 5. The impact of inflation on housing decisions

Source: Own study

Respondents were also asked directly whether they believe that purchasing an apartment was a good investment. Almost half of the respondents believe that it is a good investment (approx. 50%), and nearly 24% that it is a very good one. This decision is viewed neutrally by almost a quarter of respondents (24%). A very small proportion of them perceive purchasing a flat for investment purposes as a bad (3.3%) or very bad (1.3%) investment.

Chart 6. Do you think that buying a flat is a good or bad investment

Source: Own study

When asked why you think this is a good time to buy real estate, most people indicated that there are many apartments to choose from on the market (33.7%). A large part, as many as

32.5%, could not give an answer. However, when asked about the reasons why the respondent believe that the current time is bad to buy a flat, almost 31% pointed to the high interest rate on housing loans. Slightly fewer, as many as 29%, pointed to high prices of residential real estate.

Table 4. Why do you think this is a good time to buy real estate

No.	Reason	%
1	apartment prices are low	7.7%
2	Other	10.4%
3	it's easy to qualify for a mortgage	3.5%
4	there are many apartments available on the market	33.7%
5	I don't know	32.5%
6	general economic conditions are favorable	6.0%
7	mortgage interest rates are favorable	6.2%

Source: Own study

Table 5. Why do you think this is a bad time to buy real estate

No.	Reason	%
1	house prices are high	29.0%
2	Other	1.0%
3	there are few apartments available on the market	5.7%
4	I don't know	7.4%
5	mortgage interest rates are not favorable	30.8%
6	difficult to qualify for a mortgage loan	11.6%
7	economic conditions are generally not favorable	14.5%

Source: Own study

When asked about the frequency of discussing the situation on the real estate market, only 7% of people said that they never discuss this topic, while 50% answered sometimes and 20% - often. An interesting extension of this topic would be to obtain information about the context in which the topics are discussed and what exactly they concern.

Chart 7. How often do you discuss the issue of housing in conversations with your friends?

Source: Own study

In addition, respondents were asked a number of questions aimed at collecting preliminary results regarding the perception of price dynamics in various time horizons. When asked about price dynamics over the last 12 months, as many as approximately 79% of respondents answered prices were increasing. Only 5% believed that prices were falling, while the remaining 15.6% did not notice any changes. A question was also asked about the short and long horizon of the future. It turned out that when asked about the future, the answers differed. Fewer, 56%, predicted price increases in 2023, while twice as many, almost 14%, predicted price declines. The share of the group that expected no changes also increased (approx. 30%). The results regarding dynamics in the longest period - over the next 5 years - turned out to be even more similar. This leads to the hypothesis that in the longer term, household expectations tend to converge towards relative stability.

Table 6. Respondents' perception of price dynamics in different time horizons

No.		Price dynamics over the last 12 months	Expected price dynamics in 2023	Expected price dynamics over the next 5 years
1	were at an unchanged level	15.6%	29.9%	28.2%
2	were growing	79.4%	56.2%	53.5%
3	were falling	5.0%	13.9%	18.3%

Source: Own study

Table 7 shows the results of respondents' answers to a few simple questions related to popular theories or stories about the housing market that may show how their interpretation of recent events translates into price expectations and preferences. Our research results indicate that the shares of groups that agree with and deny these statements are relatively similar. An interesting result is provided in the case of statements number two and three. It turns out that more than

half of the respondents notice that apartment prices are rising and if they do not buy a flat now, they may not be able to afford it in the future. Even more people, almost 60%, notice the risk associated with purchasing a flat.

Table 7. Respondents' perception of price dynamics in different time horizons

No	Do you think that ...	Yes	No
1	Currently is a good time to buy an apartment, because prices will probably increase	44.7%	55.3%
2	Apartment prices are rising, if I don't buy an apartment now, I may not be able to afford it in the future	52.6%	47.4%
3	Buying an apartment involves risk	59.6%	40.4%

Source: Own study

5. Conclusions

This research is very important for expanding the knowledge about decision-making processes in the real estate market, both in Polish and world literature. The state of knowledge has been enriched in the following areas: identifying factors influencing housing decisions, examining household price expectations and searching for the relationship between housing price expectations and housing choices in relation to home purchases. Examining the tendency to perceive housing as an investment is a characteristic feature identified by Case and Shiller as a leading to a housing bubble.

The preliminary results obtained allow for the following conclusions, which should be the subject of further research:

- Approx. 65% of individuals live in the premises they own. The share of apartment renters can be rounded to approximately 20%. A large part of the sample are people living with their parents, as much as 10%.
- Interesting conclusions can be drawn from the question about the preferences of households in terms of the form of satisfying their housing needs. 55% of households were in favor of owning a flat. Only 8.9% of individuals would definitely choose renting. An interesting observation is the large share of 13.6% of respondents who do not have a clear preference.
- It turns out that a large part of the respondents in the sample do not plan to buy a flat in the coming years (as many as 44%). The rest have such plans in the near future. Within the next 2 years, 13.0% of respondents intend to purchase an apartment. 16.1%

translates these plans into a slightly later period of 2-4 years, and approximately 19.4% in 5-10 years.

- When asked what was most important when choosing an apartment, 32.8% of respondents said price. Therefore, respondents note the significant impact of budget constraints when purchasing real estate. What is also quite important is the cost of living, location and standard of the apartment. However, the standard of the building and the layout of the apartment turned out to be less important for the respondents.
- Households seem to notice a good time to purchase additional residential property. The answer to the question about the impact of inflation on housing decisions leads to the conclusion that respondents do not think in terms of investing money with the intention of protecting capital, they only notice financial constraints.
- When asked why you think this is a good time to buy real estate, most people said that there are many apartments to choose from on the market. However, when asked about the reasons why the respondent believes that the current time is bad to buy a flat, most respondents pointed to the high interest rates on housing loans and the high prices of residential real estate.
- Respondents declare that they talk about the real estate market quite often, which proves that they are interested in the situation on this market.
- In addition, respondents were asked a number of questions aimed at collecting preliminary results regarding the perception of price dynamics in various time horizons. When asked about price dynamics over the last 12 months, as many as approximately 79% of respondents answered that they felt it was positive. Only 5% believed that prices were falling. It turned out that the answers to questions about the future differed. Fewer, 56%, predicted price increases in 2023, while twice as many, almost 14%, predicted price declines. The share of the group that expected no changes also increased (approx. 30%). The results regarding dynamics over the next 5 years turned out to be even more similar. This leads to the hypothesis that in the longer term, household expectations tend to converge towards relative stability.
- More than half of the respondents notice that housing prices are rising and if they do not buy a flat now, they may not be able to afford it in the future. Even more people, almost 60%, notice the risk associated with purchasing a flat.

6. Literature :

Case, K. E., R. J. Shiller. (1988). "The Behavior of Home Buyers in Boom and Post-Boom Markets," *New England Economic Review*, Federal Reserve Bank of Boston, November-December, 29–46.

Kauko, T. (2006). Expressions of housing consumer preferences: Proposition for a research agenda. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 23(2), 92-108.

Trojanek, M. (2009). Buyers' preferences on the primary housing market in Poznań. *Acta Scientiarum Polonorum Administratio Locorum*, 8(1), 5-19.